

PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT

10

2025

PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT

Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal

10-son (2025-yil, oktabr)

Jurnal 2001-yildan chiqa boshlagan

Buxoro – 2025

PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT

Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal

2025, № 10

Jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi OAK Rayosatining 2016-yil 29-dekabrda qarori bilan **pedagogika** va **psixologiya** fanlari bo‘yicha dissertatsiya ishlari natijalari yuzasidan ilmiy maqolalar chop etilishi lozim bo‘lgan zaruriy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan.

Jurnal 2001-yilda tashkil etilgan.

Jurnal 1 yilda 12 marta chiqadi.

Jurnal O‘zbekiston matbuot va axborot agentligi Buxoro viloyat matbuot va axborot boshqarmasi tomonidan 2016-yil 22-fevral № 05-072-sonli guvohnoma bilan ro‘yxatga olingan.

Muassis: Buxoro davlat universiteti

Tahririyat manzili: 200117, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi, Buxoro shahri Muhammad Iqbol ko‘chasi, 11-uy.

Elektron manzil: nashriyot_buxdu@buxdu.uz

TAHRIR HAY‘ATI:

Bosh muharrir: Adizov Baxtiyor Rahmonovich – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Mas‘ul kotib: Sayfullayeva Nigora Zakiraliyevna – pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Xamidov Obidjon Xafizovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Begimqulov Uzoqboy Shoyimqulovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Navro‘z-zoda Baxtiyor Nigmatovich – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Ibragimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Rasulov To‘lqin Husenovich, fizika-matematika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Yanakiyeva Yelka Kirilova, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (N. Rilski nomidagi Janubiy-G‘arbiy Universitet, Bolgariya)

Andriyenko Yelena Vasilyevna pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Novosibirsk davlat pedagogika universiteti Fizika, matematika, axborot va texnologiya ta‘limi instituti, Novosibirsk, Rossiya)

Romm Tatyana Aleksandrovna pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Novosibirsk davlat pedagogika universiteti Tarix, gumanitar va ijtimoiy ta‘lim instituti, Novosibirsk, Rossiya)

Chudakova Vera Petrovna, psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (Ukraina pedagogika fanlari milliy akademiyasi, Ukraina)

Zotova Firuza Raxmatullova, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Volgabo‘yi davlat jismoniy tarbiya, sport va turizm universiteti, Rossiya)

Hamroyev Alijon Ro‘ziqulovich – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Qahhorov Siddiq Qahhorovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Mahmudova Muyassar, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Kozlov Vladimir Vasilyevich, psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Yaroslavl davlat universiteti, Rossiya)

Tadjixodjayev Zokirxo‘ja Abdusattorovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Amonov Muxtor Raxmatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

O‘rayeva Darmonoy Saidjonovna, filologiya fanlari doktori, professor

Durdiyev Durdimurod Qalandarovich, fizika-matematika fanlari doktori, professor

Mahmudov Nosir Mahmudovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Olimov Shirinboy Sharofovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Qiyamov Nishon Sodiqovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Shomirzayev Maxmatmurod Xuramovich, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Ro‘ziyeva Dilnoza Isomjonovna, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Qurbonova Gulnoz Negmatovna, pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc)

To‘xsanov Qahramon Rahimboyevich, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Nazarov Akmal Mardonovich, psixologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Dilova Nargiza Gaybullayevna, pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Jumayev Rustam G‘aniyevich, siyosiy fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Abdullayev Mehridin Junaydulloyevich, pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Sattorov Anvar Ergashovich, pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor

Nurulloev Firuz No‘monjonovich, pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor

Navruz-Zoda Layli Baxtiyorovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Fayziyeva Umida Asadovna, pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Xalikova Umida Mirovna, pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ МАСТЕРСТВО

Научно-теоретический и методический журнал

№ 10, 2025

Решением Высшей аттестационной комиссии при Кабинете Министров Республики Узбекистан от 29 декабря 2016 года журнал включён в перечень изданий, рекомендованных для публикации научных результатов статей по направлениям «Педагогика» и «Психология».

Журнал основан в 2001 году.

Журнал выходит 12 раз в год.

Журнал зарегистрирован Бухарским управлением агентства по печати и массовой коммуникации Узбекистана.

Свидетельство о регистрации средства массовой информации № 05-072 от 22 февраля 2016 г.

Учредитель: Бухарский государственный университет

Адрес редакции: 200117, Узбекистан, г. Бухара, ул. Мухаммад Икбол, 11.

E-mail: nashriyot_buxdu@buxdu.uz

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Главный редактор: Адизов Бахтиёр Рахманович – доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Ответственный редактор: Сайфуллаева Нигора Закиралиевна – доктор философии педагогических наук, доцент

Хамидов Обиджон Хафизович, доктор экономических наук, профессор

Бегимкулов Узакбай Шаимкулович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Навруз-заде Бахтиёр Нигматович, доктор экономических наук, профессор

Ибрагимов Холбой Ибрагимович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Расулов Тулкин Хусенович, доктор физико-математических наук, профессор

Янакиева Елка Кирилова, доктор педагогических наук, профессор (Болгария)

Андрюенко Елена Васильевна (Институт физико-математического, информационного и технологического образования НГПУ, Новосибирск, Россия)

Ромм Татьяна Александровна (Институт истории, гуманитарного, социального образования ФГБОУ ВО НГПУ, Новосибирск, Россия)

Чудакова Вера Петровна, кандидат психологических наук (Национальная академия педагогических наук Украины, Украина)

Зотова Фируза Рахматуллоевна, доктор педагогических наук, профессор (Поволжский государственный университет физической культуры, спорта и туризма, Россия)

Хамроев Алижон Рузикулович, доктор педагогических наук (DSc), профессор

Каххаров Сиддик Каххарович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Махмудова Мюяссар, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Козлов Владимир Васильевич, доктор психологических наук, профессор (Ярославль, Россия)

Таджиходжаев Закирходжа Абдусаттарович, доктор технических наук, профессор

Аманов Мухтор Рахматович, доктор технических наук, профессор

Ураева Дармоной Саиджановна, доктор филологических наук, профессор

Дурдиев Дурдимурод Каландарович, доктор физико-математических наук, профессор

Махмудов Насыр Махмудович, доктор экономических наук, профессор

Олимов Ширинбой Шарофович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Киямов Нишон Содикович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Шомирзаев Махматмурод Хурамович, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Рузиева Дилноза Исомжонова, доктор педагогических наук, профессор

Курбонова Гулноз Негматовна, доктор педагогических наук (DSc), профессор

Тухсанов Кахрамон Рахимбоевич, доктор филологических наук (DSc), профессор

Назаров Акмал Мардонович, доктор психологических наук (DSc), профессор

Дилова Наргиза Гайбуллаевна, доктор педагогических наук (DSc), профессор

Жумаев Рустам Ганиевич, доктор философии политических наук (PhD), доцент

Абдуллаев Мехриддин Жунайдуллоевич, доктор педагогических наук (DSc), профессор

Сатторов Анвар Эргашиевич, доктор философии педагогических наук (PhD), профессор

Нуруллоев Фируз Нумонжонович, доктор философии педагогических наук (PhD), профессор

Навруз-заде Лайли Бахтиёровна, доктор философии экономических наук (PhD), доцент

Файзиева Умида Асадовна, доктор философии педагогических наук (PhD), доцент

Халикова Умида Мировна, доктор философии педагогических наук (PhD), доцент

PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS

The scientific-theoretical and methodical journal

№ 10, 2025

By the decision of the Higher Attestation Commission under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016, the journal was included in the list of publications recommended for publishing scientific results of articles in the areas of «Pedagogy» and «Psychology».

The journal was founded in 2001.

The journal is published 12 times a year.

The journal is registered by the Bukhara Department of the Agency for Press and Mass Communication of Uzbekistan.

The certificate of registration of mass media № 05-072 of 22 February 2016

Founder: Bukhara State University

Publish house: 200117, Uzbekistan, Bukhara, Muhammad Ikbol Str., 11.

E-mail: nashriyot_buxdu@buxdu.uz

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Chief Editor: Pedagogical Sciences of Pedagogy, Prof. Bakhtiyor R. Adizov.

Editor: Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Doc. Nigora Z. Sayfullaeva

Doctor of Economics Sciences Prof. Obidjon X. Xamidov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Uzokboy Sh. Begimkulov

Doctor of Economics Sciences, Prof. Bakhtiyor N. Navruz-zade

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Holboy I.Ibragimov

Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences (DSc), Prof. Tulkin Kh. Rasulov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Yelka K. Yanakieva (Bulgaria)

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Andrienko Yelena Vasilyevna (Russia)

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Romm Tatyana Aleksandrovna (Russia)

Candidate of Psychology, Vera P. Chudakova (Kiev, Ukraina)

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Zotova Firuza Raxmatullova (Russia)

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Prof. Alijon R. Hamroev

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Siddik K. Kahhorov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof.M.Mahmudova

Doctor of Psychology, Prof. Vladimir V. Kozlov (Yaroslavl, Russia)

Doctor of Technical sciences, Prof. Zakirkhodja A. Tadjikhodjaev

Doctor of Technical sciences, Prof. Mukhtor R.Amanov

Doctor of Philology, Prof. Darmon S. Uraeva

Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Prof. Durdimurod K. Durdiev

Doctor of Economics, Prof. Nasir N. Mahmudov

Doctor of Pedagogical Science, Prof. Shirinboy Sh. Olimov

Doctor of Pedagogical Science, Prof. Nishon S. Kiyamov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Maxmatmurod X. Shomirzaev

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Dilnoza I. Ruzieva

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Gulnoz N. Qurbonova

Doctor of Philology, Prof. Qahramon R.Tuxsanov

Doctor of Psychology, Prof. Akmal M. Nazarov

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Prof. Nargiza G. Dilova

PhD in Political Sciences, Doc. Rustam G.Jumaev

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Prof. Mekhriddin J. Abdullaev

PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Anvar E. Sattorov

PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Prof. Firuz N. Nurulloev

PhD in Economics Sciences, Doc. Layli B. Navruz-zade

PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Doc. Umida A. Fayzieva

PhD in Pedagogical Sciences, Doc. Umida M. Khalikova

MUNDARIJA

Familiya I.Sh.	Mavzu	Bet
DOLZARB MAVZU		
<i>AXMEDOVA Dilnoza Eshnazar qizi, NE'MATOVA Gulchehra Uchqunovna</i>	O'quvchilarda suisidal holatlarning kelib chiqish sabablari va uni bartaraf etishning psixologik asoslari	8
PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYA		
<i>ИСМОЙЛОВА Маҳсума Нарзиқуловна, ЯРАШОВ Ихтиёр Бахтиёр угли</i>	Влияние геймификации на вовлечённость пользователей в образовательные мобильные приложения: системный подход	13
<i>AVAZYAZOVA Dilfuza Shovkatovna</i>	Xorijiy talabalarni oliy ta'limga moslashtirishning psixologik imkoniyatlari	17
<i>ATAYEVA Nilufar Saliyevna</i>	OTM talabalarining kasbiy kompetentsiyasini kredit-modul tizimi orqali takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi	22
<i>AHMEDOV Akmal Yusufovich, OXUNOVA Sarvinoz Turg'unjon qizi</i>	Bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentligini rivojlantirishda metodologik yondashuvlar	26
<i>ATAYEVA Maloxat Isakovna</i>	Ta'lim tashkilotida metodik ishning interfaol shakllari	30
<i>BABAYEVA Mahfuza Abduvoitovna</i>	O'quvchilarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	35
<i>BAXRINOVA Munisa Xusniddinovna</i>	Intuitiv qobiliyatni rivojlantirishning kognitiv va pedagogik asoslari	41
<i>BERDIYEVA Raxima Shakarboyevna</i>	Profilaktika inspektorlari kasbiy faoliyatida emotsional intellektni rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	47
<i>BADALOV Utkirbek Nomozovich</i>	The importance of practical training and dual education in developing professional competence of future engineers	51
<i>CHORIYEVA Zuhra Tolib qizi</i>	Gnoseologik yondashuv asosida talabalarda kasbiy kompetensiyani shakllantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	55
<i>DONIYOROVA Gulbahor Bobir qizi</i>	Zamonaviy maktab ta'lim paradigmasida o'qituvchi professiogrammasi va uning imijiga qo'yiladigan talablar	60
<i>ESHMAMATOV Bahodir Xolmurza o'g'li</i>	Shaxslararo munosabatlar muammosini nazariy metodologik tahlil qilish	65
<i>IMINOVA Gulxumor Ilxomjon qizi, XALIMJANOV Abduqunduz Rahimjon o'g'li</i>	Raqamli asrda diqqatni jamlash qobiliyatining o'zgarishi: doimiy ko'p vazifalilikning salbiy ta'siri	69
<i>JUMAQULOVA Saodat Quvondiq qizi</i>	Axloqiy qadriyat muammosining zamonaviy psixologik tadqiqotlarda o'rganilganligi	73
<i>KUBAYEV Ma'ruf Qosim</i>	Zamonaviy ilmiy-psixologik adabiyotlarda	80

<i>o'g'li</i>	autodestruktiv xulq-atvor tasnifi	
MARATOV Temur G'ayrat o'g'li	Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda kognitiv uslublarning namoyon bo'lishining psixologik determinantlari	84
NABIYEV Islom Karimovich	Pedagogik mahorat va pedagogik etika o'zaro bog'liqligi	89
NARSHABAYEVA Aliya Yumutbaevna	The study of the problem of diagnosing students' tolerant behavior in psychological, pedagogical, and methodological literature	94
NEGMATOVA Nigora	Pedagogik faoliyatda subyektga yo'naltirilgan ta'limdan foydalanish	99
NORMURODOVA Z.B.,	Ikki tili va bir tilda so'zlashuvchi talabalarning kasb tanlashdagi ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari	103
NORMURODOVA Adiba Alisher qizi	Oliy ta'limda talabalarning akademik mobilligini rivojlantirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari	107
PARDAQULOV Norbek	Talabalar kasbiy qobiliyatini shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-psixologik modeli	111
XOLYIGITOVA Nasiba Xabibullayevna, QAHHAROV Nuriddin Sherbek o'g'li	Yosh mutaxassislarining karyerasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishni psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlashning samarali amaliyotlari	118
QO'CHQOROV Jo'rabek Shuxrat o'g'li	O'quvchilarda ijobiy o'zini baholashni shakllantirishda pedagogik yondashuv	124
SADILLOYEV Odiljon Oripovich	O'spirinlik yoshida suitsidal xavf omillari: psixosotsial tahlil	128
SAIDOVA Nilufar Ro'zimurotovna	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini mustaqil ta'limini tashkil etishda aralash ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish usuli	134
SATTOROVA Malikaxon Abdug'affor qizi	Pedagogik jarayonning mohiyati	140
SHAROPOVA Zarnigor Tolib qizi	Ona tili darslarida tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda muammoli savollar metodining samaradorligi	144
TOSHEVA Mohinur Yusupovna	O'smirlarning stressga qarshi kurashish strategiyalarini shakllantirishda oilaviy va maktab muhitining roli	148
TURAYEVA Dilafruz Rustamboevna	O'qituvchining boshqaruv uslublari va o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi o'rtasidagi munosabat	152
TURDIEV Zafar Erkinovich	Mahkum shaxsining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari	157
UCHQUNOVA Adiba Roziq qizi	Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachilarida kreativlik darajasini tashxislovchi metodlar	161
XAMIDOV Mansurjon Abduxalilovich	O'quvchi-yoshlar ongida korrupsiyaga qarshi psixologik immunitetni rivojlantirish omillari	166
XASHIMOVA Aziza Alisherovna	OTM professor-o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini integrativ yondashuv asosida rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	173
XUDOYBERGANOVA Matluba Qulsoxatovna	Kasbiy-pedagogik mahoratni oshirishda teatr pedagogikasining metodologik asoslarini takomillashtirish	178
ZARIPOVA Zilola Erkin	Deviant xulq-atvorli o'quvchilarda ijtimoiy-	

THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF DIAGNOSING STUDENTS’ TOLERANT BEHAVIOR IN PSYCHOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL, AND METHODOLOGICAL LITERATURE

*Narshabayeva Aliya Yumutbaevna,
University of Innovation Technologies
Associate Professor of the Department of Philology PhD*

The article examines the problem of diagnosing students’ tolerant behavior, which is gaining particular importance in modern conditions due to globalization, intercultural interaction, and the need to educate a person ready for constructive dialogue. An analysis of psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature has been conducted, in which tolerance is presented as an integrative quality of personality, including cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components. Various methodological approaches and diagnostic tools used in domestic and foreign practice have been identified. It emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach that allows combining quantitative and qualitative research methods.

Keywords: *tolerance; tolerant behavior; diagnostics; students; psychological and pedagogical literature; methodological approaches.*

TALABALARNING BAG‘RIKENGLIK XULQ-ATVORINI DIAGNOSTIKALASH MUAMMOSINI PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK VA METODIK ADABIYOTLARDA O‘RGANISH

Maqolada globallashuv, madaniyatlararo o‘zaro ta’sir va konstruktiv muloqotga tayyor shaxsni tarbiyalash zarurati tufayli zamonaviy sharoitlarda alohida ahamiyat kasb etayotgan talabalarning bag‘rikenglik xulq-atvorini tashxislash muammosi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Psixologik-pedagogik va uslubiy adabiyotlar tahlili o‘tkazildi, unda bag‘rikenglik kognitiv, hissiy-qiyamatli va xulq-atvor komponentlarini o‘z ichiga olgan shaxsning integratsiyaviy sifati sifatida taqdim etilgan. Mahalliy va xorijiy amaliyotda qo‘llaniladigan turli metodologik yondashuvlar va diagnostika vositalari aniqlangan. Bu tadqiqotning miqdoriy va sifatli usullarini birlashtirishga imkon beruvchi kompleks yondashuv zarurligini ta’kidlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *bag‘rikengli, bag‘rikenglik xatti-harakati, diagnostika, talabalar, psixologik-pedagogik adabiyotlar, uslubiy yondashuvlar.*

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ТОЛЕРАНТНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ В ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ И МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

В статье рассматривается проблема диагностики толерантного поведения студентов, которая приобретает особую актуальность в современных условиях, обусловленных глобализацией, межкультурным взаимодействием и необходимостью воспитания личности, готовой к конструктивному диалогу. Проведен анализ психолого-педагогической и методической литературы, в которой толерантность представлена как интегративное качество личности, включающее когнитивный, эмоционально-ценностный и поведенческий компоненты. Выявлены различные методические подходы и диагностический инструментарий, используемые в отечественной и зарубежной практике. Подчеркивается необходимость комплексного подхода, позволяющего сочетать количественные и качественные методы исследования.

Ключевые слова: *толерантность; толерантное поведение; диагностика; студенты; психолого-педагогическая литература; методические подходы.*

Introduction. In modern educational systems, the need to cultivate students’ skills in interpersonal and intercultural interaction is becoming increasingly evident. Tolerance, as a socially significant quality, reflects not only the individual's ability to accept and respect differences but also the ability to build constructive interaction with representatives of other cultures, religions, and social groups [5, 114]. In the context of globalization and digitalization, tolerance is becoming a key condition for the successful integration of the individual into the global educational and professional space [12, 59].

In psychological and pedagogical literature, tolerance is considered as an integrative quality of personality, including three key components: cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral [10, 87; 9, 64].

In foreign pedagogy, diagnostic scales (Tolerance Scale, Intercultural Sensitivity Scale) are widely used, which allow for the quantitative assessment of students' tolerance levels [14, 245]. In domestic tradition, preference is given to the combination of tests and observations, which allows for consideration of emotional and behavioral manifestations [7, 93].

G. Soldatova identifies personal tolerance as a stable trait manifested in interpersonal interaction and proposes using psychodiagnostic methods to measure it [9, 72]. A. Asmolov connects tolerance with the process of social adaptation and emphasizes that the educational environment should create conditions for its formation [5, 118].

In the CIS countries, interest in the problem of diagnostics is increasing. Thus, the Kazakhstan researcher A. Niyazbayeva points out the importance of intercultural communication and suggests using the discursive analysis of students' statements as a diagnostic method [4, 77]. In Belarusian pedagogy, N. Grishina considers tolerance as an element of the educational system and emphasizes the need to combine quantitative tests with the analysis of educational projects [8, 48].

In Uzbekistan, significant contributions have been made by A. Abdullayev, who defines tolerance as a pedagogical category closely related to the multicultural development of society [1, 73], and I. Yoldoshev, who emphasizes the need to identify hidden forms of intolerance through the analysis of students' speech practices [2, 41]. Sh. Saidov notes that teaching German provides unique opportunities for diagnostics, as it involves modeling intercultural situations and project activities [3, 92].

Analysis of psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature shows that diagnosing students' tolerant behavior is a multifaceted process that requires a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods [15, 85]. It should take into account both the cognitive and emotional-behavioral manifestations of the individual, as well as socio-cultural factors [4, 82].

A comprehensive approach, including the use of psychometric methods, observations, analysis of educational materials, and interactive tasks, allows not only to record the level of tolerance but also to build pedagogical strategies for its formation [8, 53]. Thus, diagnostics becomes a crucial part of the educational process aimed at shaping a socially mature, open, and tolerant individual [1, 79].

Thus, it is no coincidence that the problem of diagnosing students' tolerant behavior is addressed in psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature. This is due to the need to find a balance between the theoretical understanding of the phenomenon of tolerance and its practical implementation.

Literary review.

1. Psychological and pedagogical aspect.

In psychology, tolerance is considered a personal quality that ensures harmonious interaction in society and prevents conflicts. E. V. Bondarevskaya notes that tolerance is closely linked to empathy, humanistic orientation, and the communicative culture of the individual [6, 45]. L. S. Vygotsky emphasized the social nature of personal qualities, stating that they are formed in the process of communication and joint activity [7, 92]. Consequently, diagnosing tolerance is impossible without considering the socio-cultural context and factors of the educational environment.

Modern research in pedagogy and psychology shows that tolerance includes cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components, each of which requires independent diagnostic methods [9, 72].

2. Methodological approaches.

Methodological literature identifies several key approaches to tolerance diagnostics.

The cognitive approach involves assessing students' knowledge of intercultural interaction norms, as well as their understanding of cultural differences.

The emotional-value approach is related to identifying the relationship to the “other,” the ability to empathize, emotional responsiveness, and the willingness to accept a different opinion.

The behavioral approach is based on observing students' actions, analyzing their actions in academic and extracurricular situations, which allows for the identification of real forms of tolerant or intolerant behavior.

Each of the approaches reflects only a separate aspect of tolerance, which enhances the significance of comprehensive diagnostic methods that combine questionnaires, testing, observation, and analysis of educational tasks [9, 118]. In the works of Uzbek researchers (Abdullayev, 2015; Yoldoshev, 2018) also emphasizes the need to integrate various methodological foundations for a more objective assessment of the level of students' tolerant behavior.

Thus, each approach reflects only a specific aspect of tolerant behavior, which enhances the significance of comprehensive diagnostic methods.

3. Foreign experience.

Foreign studies emphasize the intercultural dimension of tolerance. G. Allport's contact theory proves that intergroup interaction contributes to a decrease in bias and the formation of constructive behavioral patterns [10, 87]. M. Bennett (1993) developed the concept of intercultural sensitivity, in which tolerance is considered as a step towards the formation of full-fledged intercultural competence. J. Banks links tolerance education to the principles of multicultural education, emphasizing the importance of educational materials that reflect cultural diversity [12, 61].

In addition, modern approaches in pedagogy (Byram, 1997; Deardorff, 2006; Kramsch, 1993) consider tolerance not only as a social quality but also as a competency that integrates knowledge, values, and behavioral patterns.

4. CIS and Uzbekistan Studies.

In the CIS countries, tolerance is also considered an important pedagogical goal. A. Niyazbayeva indicates in her works that the formation of tolerance among students of pedagogical universities is possible through the organization of intercultural communication and joint projects [4, 77]. N. Grishina notes that the diagnosis of tolerant behavior should take into account the specifics of the multicultural educational environment and include observation of the collective activities of students [8, 48].

In Uzbekistan, A. Abdullayev defines tolerance as a key pedagogical category that ensures the formation of worldview in a multicultural society [1, 73]. I. Yoldoshev draws attention to the need to identify hidden forms of intolerance in the student environment, using the analysis of speech and behavioral practices [2, 41]. Sh. Saidov examines the role of German language teaching as an effective tool for diagnosing and forming students' intercultural competence [3, 92].

Thus, domestic and foreign authors agree that tolerance is a multidimensional phenomenon requiring multi-level diagnostic tools. Comparative analysis shows that the most promising approach is an integrative approach that combines cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral diagnostic methods and takes into account the specifics of the cultural context.

Discussion. The conducted literature analysis allows us to conclude that tolerance diagnostics encounters a number of methodological and practical difficulties. First of all, this is due to the multifaceted nature of the very concept of “tolerance,” which includes cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components [9, 72]. If, in the cognitive aspect, it is possible to determine the level of students' knowledge of the norms of intercultural interaction, then assessing emotional attitudes and behavioral manifestations presents a significantly more complex task.

Furthermore, to date, there is no unified diagnostic standard, which makes it difficult to compare the results of various studies. Existing methods - from G. U. Soldatova's tolerance index to empathy tests - only fix individual elements, creating a risk of obtaining a fragmented picture that does not reflect the holistic state of personality [6, 45]. Uzbek researcher A. Abdullayev emphasizes that such a situation makes it difficult to develop universal pedagogical programs, as the results of diagnostics are highly dependent on the chosen tools [1, 73].

Foreign authors also pay attention to this aspect. G. Allport, developing the theory of contact, noted that the limited range of diagnostic methods often does not allow for the identification of hidden forms of bias [10, 87]. M. Bennett, in the model of intercultural sensitivity, emphasized that to understand the dynamics of tolerant behavior, it is necessary to combine quantitative indicators with a qualitative analysis of interpersonal interactions [11, 29].

Modern research in the CIS (Niyazbayeva, 2017; Grishina, 2019) confirm that it is the integrated approach that allows for achieving the most reliable results. The combination of questioning, observation, self-assessment, and expert evaluation forms a multi-level understanding of students' tolerance and their readiness for intercultural interaction. In the works of I. Yoldoshev, it is also indicated that diagnostics should take into account students' speech practices, as they are indicators of hidden attitudes towards “other” [2, 41].

Thus, tolerance diagnostics should develop towards the integration of quantitative and qualitative methods, the combination of standard tests with observation, content analysis of educational communications, and pedagogical experimentation. This approach allows not only to record the level of knowledge or behavioral reactions but also to identify students' deep value orientations, which significantly increases the pedagogical effectiveness of diagnostics.

Results. Systematization of psychological-pedagogical and methodological literature allowed us to identify several key provisions that are of fundamental importance for understanding and diagnosing students' tolerant behavior.

1. Tolerance as an integrative quality of personality.

Tolerance should be considered not as an isolated trait, but as a complex personal quality that includes cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral levels [6, 45; 9, 72]. The cognitive component reflects knowledge of the norms of intercultural interaction, the emotional-value component - readiness to accept “other” and the development of empathy, and the behavioral component - the manifestation of these attitudes in specific actions and behaviors.

2. Complex nature of diagnostics.

To reliably determine the level of student tolerance, a comprehensive approach is necessary, combining various methods: testing, questionnaires, observation, expert evaluation, and analysis of student activity products [9, 118; 14, 247]. This approach allows avoiding fragmentation and fixing all levels of tolerance manifestation - from knowledge to behavioral practices.

3. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

The effectiveness of diagnostics largely depends on its adaptation to the age, socio-cultural, and professional characteristics of the audience. In the research of Uzbek scientists (Abdullaev, 2015; Yuldoshev, 2018) emphasizes that students belonging to different ethnocultural groups interpret test tasks differently and demonstrate tolerance in interpersonal communication. Therefore, diagnostics should take into account the cultural diversity and the level of professional training of future specialists.

4. Interdisciplinary approach.

Foreign experience (Allport, 1954; Banks, 2008; Byram, 1997) indicates the need for an interdisciplinary approach to diagnostics. The inclusion of pedagogical, psychological, and sociological tools expands research opportunities and allows us to consider tolerance as a complex phenomenon manifested at the intersection of personal attitudes, social experience, and educational practice.

5. Integration of diagnostics into the educational process.

The most important condition for effectiveness is the inclusion of diagnostics in pedagogical practice. It should not remain a formal procedure or episodic study, but should serve as a foundation for educational and training work [2, 41]. Diagnostic data allow the teacher to identify problem areas, plan corrective measures, and build an educational trajectory aimed at forming intercultural competence and tolerant attitudes in students.

Thus, the analysis results confirm that diagnosing students’ tolerant behavior is a complex, multifaceted process that requires comprehensive methods, an interdisciplinary approach, and integration into the learning system.

Conclusion. The conducted research has shown that diagnosing students’ tolerant behavior is not only relevant but also a methodologically complex task. On the one hand, psychological and pedagogical literature forms a rich theoretical foundation that allows us to consider tolerance as a multidimensional quality of personality, including cognitive, emotional-value, and behavioral components [7, 92; 6, 45]. On the other hand, methodological literature demonstrates the diversity of approaches and tools that, despite their value, are often fragmentary and require further systematization and adaptation to the educational process [9, 118].

The most promising direction of research and practice is a comprehensive approach, which involves a combination of quantitative and qualitative diagnostic methods. Using questionnaires, observation, testing, and analysis of students’ speech and behavioral practices in combination allows for a holistic understanding of the manifestations of tolerant behavior. At the same time, taking into account socio-cultural factors and national specific context is of particular importance, which is emphasized in the works of Uzbek researchers (Abdullayev, 2015; Yuldoshev, 2018; Saidov, 2020).

Foreign concepts (Allport, 1954; Banks, 2008; Deardorff, 2006) also confirm the necessity of an interdisciplinary approach to diagnostics that combines pedagogical, psychological, and sociological methods. This approach allows not only to record the level of students’ knowledge or behavioral reactions but also to identify their value attitudes, readiness for intercultural interaction, and ability for constructive dialogue.

Thus, the diagnostics of students’ tolerant behavior should be considered as a dynamic system organically integrated into the educational process and aimed not only at assessment but also at personality development. Its main goal is to contribute to the formation of sustainable values of dialogue, respect, mutual understanding, and cultural diversity among students.

The prospects for further research are related to:

development of unified diagnostic tools that take into account the cultural and age diversity of the student audience;

integration of digital technologies (online surveys, electronic portfolios, discourse analysis in training chats and forums) into the diagnostic process;

comparative studies of student tolerance in various CIS countries and abroad to identify universal and national-specific features.

In general, the diagnosis of tolerant behavior acts as an important element of the educational strategy of modern education, ensuring the formation of a harmonious, open-minded, and responsible personality.

References:

1. Abdullaev A. Tolerance as a pedagogical category in a multicultural society. - Tashkent: Fan, 2015. - 210 p.
2. Yoldoshev I. The Role of National and Universal Values in Educating Students' Tolerant Behavior. - Tashkent: University, 2018. - 185 p.
3. Saidov Sh. Intercultural competence and foreign language teaching: methodological aspects. - Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2020. - 224 p.
4. Niyazbayeva A. Intercultural communication as a means of forming tolerance in students of pedagogical universities. - Almaty: Kazakh University, 2017. - 176 p.
5. Asmolov A. G. Personality Psychology: A Cultural-Historical Understanding of Human Development. Moscow: Smisl, 2001. - 416 p.
6. Bondarevskaya E. V. Education as the revival of a citizen, a person of culture and morality. - Rostov-on-Don: RSU Publishing House, 1995. - 192 p.
7. Vygotsky L. S. Imagination and Creativity in Childhood. - M.: Pedagogika, 1991. - 175 p.
8. Grishina N. Educating Tolerance in a Multicultural Educational Environment. Minsk: BGU, 2019. - 142 p.
9. Soldatova G. U., Shaigerova L. A. Psychodiagnostics of Personality Tolerance. Moscow: Smisl, 2008. - 238 p.
10. Allport G. W. The Nature of Prejudice. - Cambridge, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1954. - 537 p.
11. Bennett M. J. Towards Ethnorelativism: A Developmental Model of Intercultural Sensitivity // Education for the Intercultural Experience. - Yarmouth, ME: Intercultural Press, 1993. - P. 21-71.
12. Banks J. A. An Introduction to Multicultural Education. - 5th ed. - Boston: Pearson, 2008. - 240 p.
13. Byram M. Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence. - Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, 1997. - 124 p.
14. Deardorff D. K. The Identification and Assessment of Intercultural Competence as a Student Outcome of Internationalization // Journal of Studies in International Education. - 2006. - Vol. 10, № 3. - P. 241-266.
15. Kramsch C. Context and Culture in Language Teaching. - Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1993. - 295 p.

Buxoro davlat universiteti muassisligidagi
“PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT”
ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnali
barcha ta’lim muassasalarini
hamkorlikka chorlaydi.

Pedagoglarning sevimli nashriga aylanib ulgurgan “Pedagogik mahorat” jurnali maktab, kollej, institut va universitet pedagogik jamoasiga muhim qo‘llanma sifatida xizmat qilishi, shubhasiz.

Mualliflar uchun eslatib o‘tamiz, maqola qo‘lyozmalari universitet tahririy-nashriyot bo‘limida qabul qilinadi.

Manzirimiz: Buxoro shahri, M.Iqbol ko‘chasi 11-uy
Buxoro davlat universiteti, 1-bino 2-qavat, 219-xona

Tahririyat rekvizitlari:

Moliya vazirligi g‘aznachiligi
23402000300100001010

MB BB XKKM Toshkent sh. MFO 00014 INN 201504275

BuxDU 400110860064017094100350005

Pedagogik mahorat: rivojlanamiz va rivojlantiramiz!

<p>PEDAGOGIK MAHORAT</p> <p>Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal</p> <p>2025-yil 9-son (120)</p> <p>2001-yil iyul oyidan chiqa boshlagan.</p> <p>OBUNA INDEKSI: 3070</p>	<p>Buxoro davlat universiteti nashri</p> <p>Jurnal oliy o‘quv yurtlarining professor-o‘qituvchilari, ilmiy tadqiqotchilar, ilmiy xodimlar, magistrantlar, talabalar, akademik litsey va kasb-hunar kollejlari hamda maktab o‘qituvchilari, shuningdek, keng ommaga mo‘ljallangan.</p> <p>Jurnalda nazariy, ilmiy-metodik, muammoli maqolalar, fan va texnikaga oid yangiliklar, turli xabarlar chop etiladi.</p> <p>Nashr uchun mas’ul: Nigora SAYFULLAYEVA Muharrir: Mexrigiyo SHIRINOVA Musahhh: Sarvinoz RAXIMOVA</p>	<p>Jurnal tahririyat kompyuterida sahifalandi. Chop etish sifati uchun bosmaxona javobgar.</p> <p>Bosishga ruxsat etildi 29.09.2025 Bosmaxonaga topshirish vaqti 30.09.2025 Qog‘oz bichimi: 60x84. 1/8 Tezkor bosma usulda bosildi. Shartli bosma tabog‘i – 20,6 Adadi – 100 nusxa Buyurtma № 21 Bahosi kelishilgan narxda.</p> <p>“BUKHARAHAMD PRINT” MCHJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi. Bosmaxona manzili: Buxoro shahri, J.Ikromiy MFY, Hofiz tanish Buxoriy ko‘chasi, 190 B-uy.</p>
--	---	--